

Quantum Excited States and Energy Eigenvalues

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In bound state quantum mechanics, one has statistical observables (based on $P(x)$ where P is probability) such as spatial density $d(x)$, potential energy density $V(x)d(x)$ and kinetic energy density $.5mv(x)v(x) d(x)$, where $v(x)$ is the classical velocity obtained from $.5mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E$. (Kinetic energy density can also be written as $-1/2m W(x) d/dx d/dx W(x)$ where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction). The energy of a state can be obtained by integrating these statistical observables i.e.

$$\int dx d(x) V(x) + \int dx d(x) .5mv(x)v(x) = E.$$

If one performs this integration for two different states, one may calculate the energy difference. This begs the question: why does quantum mechanics deal with conditional probabilities such as $P(p/x)$ directly related to $W(x)$? The issue perhaps begins with the appearance of $V(x)$ and E in the time independent Schrodinger equation. Kinetic energy (not kinetic energy density) should appear and be somehow linked to some motion. A question arises as to why the energy density is proportional to the spatial density i.e. Energy density = $E d(x)$? This is directly linked to the time-independent Schrodinger equation, but one may try to argue that classical energy conservation $.5mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E$ at each point x should hold in quantum mechanics with $.5mv(x)v(x)$ equal to $\sum \text{over } p \quad p^2/2m P(p/x)$ where $P(p/x) = \int \exp(ipx)/W(x)$. If one, however, considers excited states written as $W_n(x) = W_0(x)H_n(x)$ where $W_0(x)$ is the ground state wavefunction, one finds that:

$$-1/2m d/dx d/dx H_n(x) - 1/m [d/dx W_0(x)]/W_0(x) [d/dx H_n(x)] = E_1 H_n(x) \quad ((1))$$

In other words, an eigenvalue equation appears again with no $V(x)$ present. If one assumes $H_n(x)$ has physical meaning (i.e. is related to a phonon or photon), then ((1)) may suggest there is a physical principle in place, i.e. the idea that one must have a "constant" energy at each point x . Here E_1 is strictly kinetic energy (although not all of it). This "principle" has consequences as it restricts the values of E_1 (i.e. discrete eigenvalues) and leads often to a periodic $H_n(x)$ which has direct effect on kinetic energy density and potential energy density. Thus, having $H_n(x)$ interact with $W_0(x)$ to produce a constant energy E_1 times $H_n(x)$ does affect kinetic and energy densities at each x point, just not kinetic energy itself (it is constant i.e. E_1). The purpose of this note is to examine this possible principle behind quantum mechanics.

Statistical Probabilities

In classical statistics, one often uses full probabilities $P(x)$ and $P(p)$ where x is position and p momentum. For bound quantum states, these probabilities exist too, namely $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$ and $P(p)=f_p*f_p$, where $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p \text{ } f_p \exp(ipx)$. This has often led to the question in the literature: why does one need $W(x)$, the square root of the spatial density? If one measures $d(x)$ experimentally, one may immediately obtain potential and kinetic energy densities as well as the average energy of the system, i.e. :

$$V(x)P(x), \quad .5mv(x)v(x)P(x) \text{ and } E= \text{Integral } dx \quad V(x)P(x) + .5mv(x)v(x) P(x).$$

(In the literature, it is suggested that soft measurement of $P(x)$ can be performed.)

One may ask whether there is another principle at work. Even with the time-independent Schrodinger equation, $HW(x) = E_n W(x)$, one focuses on the discrete sets of E_n 's and considers boundary conditions leading to this discreteness. In this note, we argue that perhaps the idea of having a constant E in x space (which leads directly to the energy eigenvalue equation) may represent a physical principle.

At first, one may argue that such a constant E at each x represents nothing more than classical conservation of energy i.e.:

$$.5mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((1b))$$

This classical conservation equation, however, is based on the idea of force= $-d/dx V(x)$ governing the motion of a particle which has a specific momentum at x . This is not the quantum mechanical picture, however, one may write:

$$-1/2m [d/dx d/dx W(x)]/W(x) = .5mv(x)v(x) \quad ((2)) \text{ for a bound state}$$

For $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p \text{ } f_p \exp(ipx)$:

$$-1/2m [d/dx d/dx W(x)]/W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } p^2/2m f_p \exp(ipx) / W(x) \quad ((3))$$

Thus, a conditional average of $p^2/2m$ i.e. $\text{Sum over } p \text{ } p^2/2m P(p/x)$ has the same x dependence as $.5mv(x)v(x)$. In bound state quantum mechanics, however, there is also the conditional average of p i.e. $\text{Sum over } p \text{ } p f_p \exp(ipx) / W(x)$. This does not, in general follow a conservation equation such as ((1.b)) (It only does so for the ground state oscillator.) Thus, ((1b)) is a little misleading when applied to quantum mechanics. Nevertheless, ((1b)) does represent classical energy conservation, and one may argue that it is applied in "some way" to quantum mechanics, so there is really no new principle at work.

If one considers an excited state, however, things seem a little different. Consider writing $W_n(x)=W_0(x)H_n(x)$ where $W_0(x)$ is the ground state wavefunction. If $W_0(x)H_n(x)$ is simply a mathematical procedure, then there is no argument to present. $H_n(x)$, however, may represent the effect of an oscillatory particle such as a phonon or photon used to excite the ground state.

It is known the ground state obeys: $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W_0(x) + V(x)W_0(x) = E_0 W_0(x)$

Thus, all direct interaction with $V(x)$ is "utilised" by $W_0(x)$. If one inserts $W_0(x)H_n(x)$ into the time-independent Schrodinger equation and divides by $W_0(x)$, one finds $H_n(x)$ only appears as part of the kinetic energy term: $[-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W_n(x)]/W_n(x)$ i.e.

$$-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} H_n(x) - 1/m [\frac{d}{dx} W_0(x)]/W_0(x) [\frac{d}{dx} H_n(x)] = E_1 H_n(x) \quad ((4))$$

$H_n(x)$ contributes a constant E_1 to the kinetic energy at each point x . This is in keeping with the idea that it does interact directly with $V(x)$. The total kinetic energy is given by:

$$[-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W_n(x)]/W_n(x) = (E_0 - V(x)) + E_1 \quad ((5))$$

Thus, it is the ground state $W_0(x)$ which supplies the Newton-like behaviour of the overall kinetic energy (not kinetic energy density) as it is the part which interacts with $V(x)$. $H_n(x)$ interacts with $W_0(x)$ (and so indirectly with $V(x)$) and shows no Newton like behaviour given by ((1b)).

Nevertheless, it produces a constant E_1 of kinetic energy throughout space.

In this note, we argue that perhaps there is a physical principle related to E being independent of x (and p as well). It should be noted there are consequences of ((4)) with E_1 at all x . First, this leads to discrete E_1 values and secondly, one may obtain a periodic $H_n(x)$. This has a direct affect on spatial density $W_n(x)W_n(x) = W_0(x)W_0(x)H_n(x)H_n(x)$ as well as on kinetic and potential energy densities. Thus, in terms of these energy densities, one does have x dependence due to $H_n(x)$. One may argue that E_1 appears as a constant in ((4)) in order to have an overall constant $E = E_0 + E_1$ at each point x , and this follows from classical energy conservation ((1b)). It seems, however, that ((4)) represents a physical coupling of an oscillating particle $H_n(x)$ (say a photon or phonon) and the ground state wavefunction in such a way that a constant kinetic energy in space is produced.

Spatial Picture

It seems there is a certain probability $P(x)$ for the quantum particle to appear at x . If it does, its energy is E regardless of the value of x . $P(x)$ changes in space as: $\frac{d}{dx} P(x) = P(x) u(x)$ (where $u(x) = [\frac{d}{dx} W(x)]/W(x) = \langle i p \text{ conditional} \rangle$. $u(x)$ does not follow Newtonian mechanics, but $\langle p^2/2m \text{ conditional} \rangle$ does. Interestingly, E is related to the form of $W(x)$ (for the kinetic energy), but this same $W(x)$ contributes to $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$. In other words, $\langle i p \text{ conditional} \rangle$ (an average based on $W(x)$) governs changes in $P(x)$, while $\langle p^2/2m \text{ conditional} \rangle$ is restricted to combine with $V(x)$ to ensure a constant E at each x .

Momentum Space

It should be noted that if one takes the time-independent Schrodinger equation and writes both $V(x)$ and $W_n(x)$ as Fourier series, one obtains:

$$p^2/2m f_p + \sum_{j+k=p} V_j f_k = E_n f_p \quad ((6))$$

Here V_j is the j th Fourier transform of $V(x)$. For each p , the same E_n appears in ((6)), thus, E_n is not dependent on p . In previous notes, it was argued this suggests a cycling resonance as each f_p is created through the interaction of other f_k 's with V_j 's. The cycling time is the same for each f_p .

The Case of $\text{Exp}(iEt)$

For bound state problems, the time dependence of $W_n(x,t)$ is $\text{exp}(iE_n t)$. In other words, E_n is directly related to a physical periodic. This cycling is not linked to x and p which may be why E_n or even parts of E_n (in the $W_n=W_0(x)H_n(x)$ case) appear as eigenvalues in quantum mechanical bound state problems.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest there may be a physical principle associated with bound state quantum mechanics related to the idea of E being constant in space (independent of x and p). (This may be directly related to the idea that energy appears as a frequency in $\text{exp}(iEt)$). This may suggest why energy eigenvalues appear in the time-independent Schrodinger equation. One may argue that E is not dependent on x because of classical conservation of energy at each x with kinetic energy based on a conditional average of $p^2/2m$. Examining the interaction of $W_0(x)$ and $H_n(x)$ in $W_n(x)=W_0(x)H_n(x)$ and assuming $H_n(x)$ represents a photon or phonon (etc), also leads to an equation with an eigenvalue of E_1 which is space independent and purely kinetic. Thus, one is not "using" an energy eigenvalue because part of the kinetic energy converts to potential energy as one moves from one x point to another. The same value E_1 is present at each point. Furthermore, the imposition of a constant E_1 may cause periodicity in $H_n(x)$ which affects the density $W_n(x)W_n(x)$ and in turn kinetic and potential energy densities. Thus, even though $H_n(x)$ only contributes to the kinetic energy term of the time-dependent Schrodinger equation $-1/2m d/dx d/dx W_n(x)$, it is indirectly affecting potential energy density which would suggest some interaction with $V(x)$ and not a constant E_1 at first glance. Thinking in terms of the time dependent portion of $W_n(x,t)$, one has $\text{exp}(iE_0t) \text{exp}(iE_1t)$ where E_0 and E_1 add as frequencies to create a new overall frequency E_0+E_1 .